

DETERMINATION OF METAPHORIC PERCEPTIONS OF GERMAN TEACHER CANDIDATES IN THE TURKEY TOWARDS GERMAN READING AND WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract:

The first stage in the learning process is the perception of the learning input by the student. This perception, which develops due to many factors in the learning process, has also great importance in skill acquisition. Therefore, the perception of basic language skills by the students, determining how the students make sense of the skills may contribute to foreign language teaching. In this context, the aim of this study is to determine the perceptions of prospective German teachers about reading and writing skills that enable the use of language. Phenomenology pattern was used in the study. The research data were collected through a form prepared by the researcher. The form contains two sentences that should be completed in order to determine the metaphoric perceptions and reasons of the candidates. The data obtained were evaluated by content analysis. Each skill was analyzed separately. In the study, under 58 metaphors related to reading skills, ten categories were developed: "development, vocabulary learning, opening to different worlds, giving pleasure, being difficult to understand, removing from context, working the brain, requiring continuity, developing pronunciation, being important". Eleven categories have been developed under 61 metaphors for writing skills. "being difficult, giving importance to grammar, giving pleasure as you succeed, creativity, freedom, creating integrity, requiring a lot of labor, being the most important, being the easiest way to express thoughts, being permanent, new things learning".

Keywords: reading skills, writing skills, teaching German, metaphoric perception, German teacher candidates

Özet:

Öğrenme sürecindeki ilk aşama öğrenme girdisinin öğrenci tarafından algılanmasıdır. Öğrenme sürecinde birçok faktöre bağlı olarak gelişen bu algı, beceri ediniminde de büyük bir öneme sahiptir. Dolayısıyla öğrenciler tarafından temel dil becerilerinin

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algılanma biçimi, öğrencilerin becerileri nasıl anlamlandırdıklarının belirlenmesi yabancı dil öğretimine katkı sağlayabilecektir. Bu bağlamda bu çalışmanın amacı Almanca öğretmen adaylarının dilin kullanımını sağlayan okuma ve yazma becerilerine ilişkin algılarını belirlemektir. Çalışmada fenomenoloji deseni kullanılmıştır. Araştırma verileri araştırmacı tarafından hazırlanan bir form aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Formda adayların becerilere ilişkin metaforik algılarını ve gerekçelerini belirlemek amacıyla tamamlanması gereken iki cümle yer almaktadır. Elde edilen veriler içerik analizi yapılarak değerlendirilmiştir. Her bir beceri için ayrı ayrı analizler yapılmıştır. Çalışmada okuma becerisine ilişkin 58 metafor altında "gelişme, kelime öğrenme, farklı dünyalara açılmak, zevk vermek, anlaması güç olması, bağlamdan çıkarma, beyni çalıştırma, süreklilik gerektirmesi, telaffuz geliştirme, önemli olması" olmak üzere on kategori; yazma becerisine ilişkin 61 metafor altında "zor olması, dilbilgisine önem verme, başardıkça zevk vermesi, yaratıcılık, özgürlük, bütünlük oluşturma, çok emek gerektirmesi, en önemli olması, düşünceleri dile getirmenin en kolay yolu, kalıcı olması, yeni şeyler öğrenme" olmak üzere on bir kategori geliştirilmiştir.

Anahtar kelimeler: okuma becerisi, yazma becerisi, Almanca öğretimi, metaforik algı, Almanca öğretmen adayları

1. Introduction

The aim of foreign language teaching is to provide the student with basic language skills and the use of language. This situation is stated in educational institutions in the foreign language education and training regulation of the Ministry of National Education that the aim of foreign language teaching is to enable individuals to acquire listening, speaking, writing and reading skills and to develop positive attitudes towards foreign language teaching (MEB, 2009). As stated in the regulation, the ability of students to develop positive attitudes towards language skills is a matter of how they perceive the foreign language in question. Therefore, the perception of language skills by the students and determining how the students make sense of the skills may contribute to foreign language teaching. Reading and writing in foreign language teaching are tried to be gained by the students with the lessons like "*Reading skills course, a writing skills course, advanced reading and writing skills. The reading action is not only decoding linguistic signs; it is also the process of using and making sense of information already stored in memory. While reading, general and contextual information is activated and some thematic subjects and text types construct an understanding action*" (Huneke & Steinig, 2010: 135). As Huneke and Steinig pointed out, the process of reading is not only about analyzing and interpreting linguistic codes at a simple level, but also analyzing the text by employing the knowledge and experiences that existed in the cognitive world of the reader.

Writing is the expression of emotions, thoughts, wishes and events with symbols in accordance with certain rules (Güneş, 2013). Writing is a process that is put into action with cognitive, affective and creative elements (Graf, 2014, p. 38). Because reading and

writing are interrelated, developing one skill can contribute to the development of another. Therefore, the perception of this language skill by the students, determining how the students make sense of the skills may contribute to foreign language teaching. One way to determine how students perceive language skills and what they mean to them is to use metaphors. *“Metaphors are a method that allows individuals to use some of the concepts they use in their daily lives in explaining concepts or situations they cannot explain”* (Bozpolat, 2015: 320). Metaphor studies can help prospective teachers to recognize themselves and to activate their mental processes. By means of metaphors, prospective teachers will have the opportunity to express themselves freely and perform intellectual activities that they have not thought or realized before (Kana & Yıldırım, 2018: 279). In this context, in this study, it was tried to determine the metaphors of the prospective German teachers about their reading and writing skills and the reasons, common characteristics, positive and negative ones of these metaphors. For this purpose, the research question of this study is as follows;

- What are the metaphors developed by prospective German language teachers about reading and writing German language skills?

Sub research questions:

- What are the positive and negative metaphoric perceptions of prospective German teachers about reading skills and which conceptual categories are these classified?
- What are the positive and negative metaphoric perceptions of the prospective German teachers about writing skills and which conceptual categories are they included in?

Generally, studies of metaphor in teaching Turkish language skills as a foreign language in Turkey is made, however, studies on English and German language skills as a foreign language have not been found in the literature. Therefore, this study is thought to contribute to the field.

2. Material and Methods

In this study, one of the qualitative research methods, a phenomenology pattern was used. Phenomenology examines individuals' perceptions of any fact or event, the meanings attributed to events, and individual experiences. In addition to this, it is tried to obtain with this method a psychological essence related to a case or situation which is experienced by the participants (Baş & Akturan, 2013). Phenomenology, which is based on the experiences and perceptions of individuals, aims to reveal common meanings related to the experiences of individuals with the help of concepts (Aslan, 2018). Therefore, in this study, it is tried to investigate the meanings attributed to the reading and writing skills of the participants.

2.1. Research Group

The research group of this study consisted of a total of 71 pre-service teachers who were studying in German Language Teaching Department of Faculty of Education, Muğla Sıtkı

Koçman University in the spring term of 2018-2019 academic years. The selection of the research group was made in accordance with the easily accessible case sampling which is one of the purposeful sampling methods (Yıldırım, Şimşek, 2008: 113). Easily accessible sampling is the preference of the participants selected as a research group in order to obtain the data more easily and conduct the research more easily and practically (Kurtuluş, 2010). Participation in the research was based on volunteering.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

The research data were collected through a form prepared by the researcher. The form contains two sentences that need to be completed in order to determine the metaphorical perceptions and rationales of the candidates regarding the skills: "Writing skill is similar tobecause...", "Reading skill is similar tobecause..." With this form, prospective teachers are expected to indicate their perceptions of these two skills together with their reasons through metaphors. Thus, it was tried to determine which metaphors related to the reading and writing skills of the prospective German teachers developed and what the reasons for these metaphors are.

2.4. Data Collection and Analysis

At this stage of the study, the forms given to the students were numbered in order to determine the metaphors in which prospective teachers expressed their perceptions about reading and writing skills. The data of the study were analyzed by content analysis method. Since each skill was handled separately, analyses were performed in two rounds. Firstly, the metaphors developed for each skill were listed. Then categories were formed by considering the analogy aspects of the metaphors. Miles and Huberman's (1994) formula was used to calculate the reliability of the study. This formula; Reliability = consensus / consensus + disagreement". Accordingly, if the agreement between experts and researcher evaluations is 90% and above, a desired level of reliability is provided (cited in Saban, 2008: 430). In order to determine the reliability of the study, 64 metaphors for reading skills and 71 metaphors for writing skills were sent to a field expert and were asked to be listed these metaphors under the categories created by the researcher. As a result of the comparison of the pairings of the researcher and the expert, it was found that the four metaphors, namely "pre-sleep, river, song memorization, adoption" developed for reading skills, were shown in different categories. Accordingly, the reliability of reading skill data was calculated as $60/60 + 4 \times 100 = 93.7\%$. The metaphors of, "poetry and intelligence" developed for writing skills are shown in different categories. According to this result, the reliability of writing skill data was calculated as $69/69 + 2 \times 100 = 97.1\%$. Therefore, it can be said that the study has a high reliability rate.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Metaphors Developed by the Prospective German Teachers about Reading Skills

Number	Student	Metaphor	Number of Repetition of Metaphor
1.	E1	Bookshelf	1
2.	K2	Vocabulary	1
3.	K3, K48	Life	2
4.	K4	New talking	1
5.	K5	Rhyme	1
6.	K6	Have a rest	1
7.	E7	Machine oil	1
8.	K8	Resting the spirit	1
9.	K9	Evolution	1
10.	K10	Culture	1
11.	K11	Song	1
12.	K12	The happiest child in the World	1
13.	K13	Ability indicator	1
14.	K14	Adoption	1
15.	K15	Stairs	1
16.	K16	Rubik's cube	1
17.	K17	Memorize the song	1
18.	E18	Solve puzzle	1
19.	K19	Colors	1
20.	K20, K44, E61, K51	Deep sea	4
21.	K21	Analysis	1
22.	E22	Labyrinth	1
23.	K23	Cycling	1
24.	E24	Jigsaw	1
25.	K25	Dreaming	1
26.	E26	Key	1
27.	K27	Addicted	1
28.	K28	Wake up every morning	1
29.	E29, K60	River	2
30.	K30	Pronunciation development	1
31.	K31	phone without internet	1
32.	K32	The most beautiful habit	1
33.	K33	Deep ocean	1
34.	K34	Part of a whole	1
35.	E35	Eat	1
36.	K36	Baby	1
37.	E37	Brainless body	1
38.	E38	Hunger for knowledge	1
39.	K39	Notes	1
40.	K40	Ghost	1
41.	K41	Hot pepper	1
42.	K42	Monday	1
43.	K43, K64	Sleep	2
44.	K45	Chewing gum	1
45.	K46	To follow a path	1

46.	K47	Bag	1
47.	E49	before sleeping	1
48.	K50	Language processing	1
49.	K52	Puzzle	1
50.	K53	Water	1
51.	K54	Brain	1
52.	K55	Pearl	1
53.	K56	Novel	1
54.	K57	Sun	1
55.	K58	Story	1
56.	K59	Flower	1
57.	K62	Appetizers	1
58.	K63	World	1

3.1. Categories of Metaphors Developed for Reading Skills

When the data related to reading skill obtained from 64 German pre-service teachers were analyzed, it was seen that pre-service teachers developed 58 metaphors related to reading skill. These metaphors were grouped under 10 categories: “development, vocabulary learning, opening up to different worlds, giving pleasure, being difficult to understand, removing from context, working the brain, requiring continuity, developing pronunciation, being important”. Each category is tabulated and explained with metaphors and reasons.

Table 2: Metaphors and Reasons for Development Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Bookshelf	Developing as you read	Development
Life	Learning as you read	
Evolution	Development of the person	
Culture	Learning as you read	
Song	Increased of the skill, fast reading	
Stairs	One step increase in reading in each text	
Key	Opening information doors	
Deep ocean	Advancing as you read	
Baby	Grows if necessary attention is shown.	
Story	Learning as you read	

In Table 2, ten metaphors have been developed in the category of development: library, life, development, culture, song, stairs, key, deep ocean, baby, story. When the metaphors' analogy direction is examined, it is seen that reading skill is justified as developing the person and learning as he/she read. Therefore, it was found that according to the students reading skill improves both linguistic knowledge and general culture. The participant 4k with the expression "*Reading is like a story. Because as we read, we learn something.*" states that reading skill improves the person, since new information is learned from the texts. The participant 1k with his analogy "*Reading is like stairs. Because, as you approach one step to the top on each ladder, your reading skill increases one step in each text*" stated that reading skill increases by reading with each text. And participant 1k with his

expression “*Reading skill is like a song. Because the more you read, the higher your skill and the faster you read.*” emphasized that the speed of comprehension and reading increases as the text is read.

Table 3: Metaphors and Reasons for Vocabulary Learning Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Vocabulary	Learn new words	
New talking	Not being able to pronounce every word	Vocabulary
River	Flow of the words when reading	learning
Life	Learning new things at any moment	

In Table 3, vocabulary learning category includes the metaphors of “vocabulary, new talking, river and life”. When these metaphors are analyzed, it is understood that reading skill generally contributes to the students' learning new words and the development of their pronunciation. Participant 1k “*Reading skill is like vocabulary. Because it is possible to learn unknown words and develop vocabulary, while reading.*” stated that unknown words can be removed from the context and new words are learned during the reading process. Participant 1k with this analogy “*reading skill is like talking new. Because being unable to pronounce every word you see makes you feel like new talking or reading.*” expressed that it was difficult to pronounce when there were words that were not previously encountered in the text.

Table 4: Metaphors and Reasons for Opening up to Different Worlds

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Have a rest	Go to another World	
Resting the spirit	Finding yourself in another World	
Hunger for knowledge	To realize that you don't know as you read	Opening up to
Sun	Feeling learning as you read	different worlds
Deep sea	Opening up new horizons	
World	Opening up to different worlds	
Before sleeping	Door opening to unique dreams	
Sleep	Door opening to unique dreams	

In Table 4, in the category of opening to different worlds was developed the metaphors of “have rest, resting the spirit, hunger for knowledge, sun, deep sea, World, before sleeping and sleep”. From these metaphors, it is understood that reading skill improves students' horizons and gives them the opportunity to see different thoughts. Participant 4k with this expression “*The ability to read is like the world. Because as I read it, I feel like I have opened up to the world of different people, people with different languages and cultures.*” emphasized that new cultures are introduced through reading and that people are aware of different worlds. Participant 4e with this sentence “*Reading skill is like the sea. Because as you read, you open up to new horizons.*” stated that the act of reading provides the person to think and produce new ideas.

Table 5: Metaphors and Reasons for Giving Pleasure Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
The happiest child in the world	Understanding text after reading text	Giving Pleasure
Cycling	Having fun	
Addicted	Being dependent as you read	
Water	Enjoying as you read	
Appetizers	Being easier	

Table 5 includes the metaphors of “the happiest child in the World, cycling, addicted, water, appetizers”. When these metaphors and their reasons are examined, it can be said that students enjoy reading process and their desire to read increases gradually. Participant 1k with her statement *“Reading is like the happiest child in the world. Because it’s a feeling when I realize that I understand after reading a text”* emphasized that she was very happy after reading the text. Participant 4k with this analogy *“reading is like water. Because as people read, the desire to read occurs”* stated that the reading process gives pleasure and creates more desire to read.

Table 6: Metaphors and Reasons for Being Difficult to Understand Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Rubik's cube	Complexity of sentence and word structures	Being difficult to understand
Deep sea	Getting lost in the depths	
Hot pepper	Difficult to understand	
Sea	Having tides	
Novel	Understanding requires care	

In Table 6, in the category of being difficult to understand were developed metaphors “rubik’s cube, deep sea, hot pepper, sea, novel”. From these metaphors, it is understood that students have difficulty reading a German text, have difficulty in solving sentence structures, and show great care to understand the text. Participant 1k stated with *“reading like rubik’s cube, because sentences, structures and words are mixed. It must be solved.”* that it is very difficult to understand of structural features of German and mixed words in texts when reading. Participant 3k with this expression *“Reading skill is like hot pepper. because at first it is difficult, but then the pain goes away, the taste remains beauty.”* stated that this process was difficult when she first read. Participant 4k with this analogy *“Reading is like a novel. Because it requires care to understand.”* emphasized the need to be careful and laborious to understand the text in the reading process.

Table 7: Metaphors and Reasons for Removing from Context Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Solve puzzle	Removing missing pieces from context	Removing from context
Colors	Changing of the meaning from person to person	
Analysis	Analyzing text by understanding words	
Jigsaw	To understand the text by combining sentences	
Part of a whole	Not understanding the missing pieces	
Notes	Integrity occurs when words come together	
Puzzle	Extracting the meaning from words	

In Table 7, in the removing from context category the metaphors of “solve puzzle, colors, analysis, jigsaw, part of whole, notes and puzzle” were developed. When the reasons of these metaphors are examined, it is seen that the students develop strategies during the reading process and remove the words or sentences they do not understand from the context. Participant 1e with the expression “*Reading skill is like solving puzzles. Because you need to take advantage of context to complete the missing pieces.*” stated that points that are not understood in the text, explanations in the text of unknown words, can be understood by decoding. Participant 1e with this sentence “*reading skill is like a jigsaw. Because by combining each sentence, we understand what the text means*” emphasized that by combining the power of expression of each sentence by looking at the text in a holistic way, meaning can be extracted. Participant 3k “*reading skill is like notes Because when it comes together like sheet music, integrity occurs.*” stated that the meaning is removed from this context because there is an integrity in the text.

Table 8: Metaphors and Reasons for the Working the Brain Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Machine oil	Refreshing the brain while reading	
Ability indicator	Reading is a talent	
Labyrinth	Finding ways in different meanings	Working
Dreaming	Extract meaning from symbols	the Brain
Ghost	Learning new things without realizing it	
Language processing	Learning grammar and vocabulary	
Brain	Expression of thoughts	

In Table 8, in the category of working the brain the metaphors of “machine oil, ability indicator, labyrinth, dreaming, ghost, language processing and brain” have been developed. When these metaphors and analogies are analyzed, it is understood that reading skill has many functions according to the students, it provides the brain to work and contributes to the learning of grammar and vocabulary. Participant 1e “*Reading skill is like machine oil. Because if we imagine our brain as a machine when this machine rusts, we lubricate it and make it work again. Reading has such an effect on our brains.*” stated that reading helps the brain to work, mental processes become functional through reading. Participant 1k “*Reading skill is like dreaming. Because even if we don’t understand everything, we deduce meanings from symbols.*” stressed that meaning can be derived from context. Participant 3k with this expression “*reading is like the processing of language. Because grammar and vocabulary are learned.*” stated that can be understood how the structural features of the language are used functionally and the word is learned through the text.

Table 9: Metaphors and Reasons for Requiring Continuity Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Wake up every morning	Requiring continuity	
Sleep	Occurrence of read request	
Chewing gum	Getting used to over time	
To follow a path	Advancing as you read	Requiring
Bag	To slip when you stop reading	continuity
Sea	Occurrence of read request	
River	Going away while reading	

In Table 9, the metaphors of “waking up every morning, sleep, chewing gum, to follow a path, bag, sea, river” were developed in the category of requiring continuity. From these metaphors, it is understood that the development of reading skill is continuous and progress can be made over time. Participant 3k *“reading skill is like chewing gum. Because it is hard at first, but the more you chew, the more you chew.”* stated that the reading process was difficult at first, but that the desire to read increased as it progressed. Participant 2k *“Reading is like waking up every morning. Because it requires continuity.”* emphasized the need for continuous reading for the development of reading skills. Participant 3k *“Reading is like a bag. Because the moment you pull the zipper, you forget it. As soon as you stop reading, you forget the language”* stated that there might be a decline in their knowledge of the language when the reading was interrupted.

Table 10: Metaphors and Reasons for the Developing Pronunciation Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Rhyme	Attention to intonation	
Developing pronunciation	Development of pronunciation while reading	
River	To flow the words when reading	Developing
Adoption	Comprehension of pronunciation	Pronunciation
Sing	Read as fast as you read	

In Table 10, metaphors of “rhyme, developing pronunciation, river, adoption and sing” were developed in the category of developing pronunciation. According to the students' views, it is understood from these metaphors that reading skills contribute to the development of pronunciation and intonation skills. Participant 1k with this *“reading skill is like rhyme. Because we read by looking at the emphasis and punctuation.”* stressed the importance of reading and punctuation, and stated that the text should make sense to both the reader and the listening person. Participant 2k *“reading skill is like developing pronunciation. Because it helps me improve my vocabulary and pronunciation ”* stated that reading contributes to the pronunciation of the words correctly.

Table 11: Metaphors and Reasons for the Category Being Important

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Phone without internet	without reading is language ineffective	
The most beautiful habit	Failure to develop without reading	
Eat	To be beneficial	Being
Brainless body	Language system does not work without reading	important
Pearl	Developing as you read	
Flower	Reading is important	

In Table 11, the metaphors of “phone without internet, the most beautiful habit, eat, brainless body, pearl, flower” have been developed in the category of being important. When the reasons of these metaphors are examined, it is seen that students care about reading skill and think that reading skill is important for language development. Participant 2k *“reading is like an phone without internet, because we learn the language but without reading it doesn’t have much effect.”* stated that reading is very important in language teaching. Participant 4k *“reading is like a flower. Because when we look at a flower, if we first see the colored part, reading is essential for a language to show itself.”* emphasized that reading skill is the occurrence of language. Participant 2k *“reading is like the most beautiful habit. Because we can’t improve ourselves without reading.”* stated that reading is a very important skill to develop oneself.

Table 12: Metaphors Developed by the Prospective German Teachers about Writing Skills

Number	Student	Metaphor	Number of Repetition of Metaphor
1.	E1	Steep rock	1
2.	K2	Book	1
3.	E3	Job application	1
4.	K4	Rain	1
5.	E5	Paint	1
6.	K6	Math	1
7.	K7	Clean Air	1
8.	K8	Being creative	1
9.	E9	Painting	1
10.	K10	First steps of a baby	1
11.	K11	Loop	1
12.	K12	Latch	1
13.	K13	Information	1
14.	K14	The basis of language	1
15.	K15, K19, K21, K47, E53, K64	Freedom	6
16.	K16	Chain	1
17.	K17	Communication	1
18.	K18	Life	1
19.	E20	A stain that leaves a mark	1
20.	K22	Tattoo	1
21.	K23, K27, K37, E43	Art	4
22.	K24	Being a painter	1
23.	E25	Ocean	1

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24.	K26	Grammar development	1
25.	E28	Attract Eyeliner	1
26.	K29	Stairs	1
27.	K30	The mirror of feelings	1
28.	K31	Vital organ	1
29.	K32	Letter	1
30.	K33	Putting information on paper	1
31.	E34	Build	1
32.	K35	Make-up	1
33.	K36	Eat	1
34.	K38	Traffic signs	1
35.	E39	Heartless body	1
36.	K40	Tree	1
37.	K41	Soil	1
38.	K42	Production	1
39.	K44	Bed	1
40.	K45	Sport	1
41.	K46	Playing ball	1
42.	K48	Eat	1
43.	K49	Friday	1
44.	K50	Basic stone	1
45.	K51	Hold pen	1
46.	K52	Intelligence	1
47.	K54	Trace	1
48.	K55	Something that requires skill	1
49.	E56	Snowball	1
50.	K57, K58	Jigsaw	2
51.	K59	Branches of a flower	1
52.	K60	Mirror	1
53.	K61	Sea	1
54.	K62	Field	1
55.	K63, K67	Poem	2
56.	K65	Mill	1
57.	K66	imagination	1
58.	K68	Learn language	1
59.	K69	Dream	1
60.	K70	Thinking	1
61.	E71	Artist	1

3.2. Categories of Metaphors Developed for Writing Skills

When the data about the writing skill obtained from 71 pre-service teachers were analyzed, it was seen that the pre-service teachers developed 61 metaphors related to the writing skill. These metaphors are classified under 11 categories: “difficulty, giving importance to grammar, giving pleasure as you succeed, creativity, freedom, creating integrity, requiring a lot of labor, being the most important, being the easiest way to express thoughts, being permanent, learning new things”. Each category is tabulated and explained with metaphors and reasons.

Table 13: Metaphors and Reasons for Difficulty Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Steep rock	Writing by rules is a difficulty	Difficulty
Ocean	To be infinite	
Art	Not an easy skill	
Hold pen	Not to develop immediately, takes time	
Trace	to be difficult	
Something that requires skill	Difficult to win	
Jigsaw	To being complex sentence structures	
Artist	To be difficult	

In Table 13, the metaphors of “steep rock, ocean, art, hold pen, trace, something that requires skill, jigsaw and artist” have been developed in the category of difficulty. When the reasons of metaphors are examined, it is understood that writing skills are difficult for students, it is not easy to use German grammatical structures while writing and it is difficult to gain writing skills. Participant 1e *“Writing skill is like a steep rock. Because writing in accordance with the rules is like climbing that rock.”* stated that it is very difficult to write according to the rules of language in writing skills. Participant 2k *“Writing skills are like art. Because it is not an easy skill.”* emphasized that not everyone can perform art as well as it cannot be easily written in a foreign language. Participant 4e *“Writing is like an artist. Because writing in a foreign language is an artistly movement.”* stated that someone who wrote in a foreign language would have achieved great success.

Table 14: Metaphors and Reasons for giving importance to grammar Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Job application	Paying attention to grammar while writing	Giving importance to grammar
Math	Care about choosing the right Word	
Information	Learning grammar while writing	
Grammar development	Using structures in sentence building	
Traffic signs	Writing in accordance with the rules	

Table 14 shows the metaphors of “job application, math, information, grammar development, traffic signs” in the giving importance to grammar category. It is understood from the reasons of the metaphors that the students take great care to use the grammar rules correctly in their writing skills and learn the grammar rules better in this process. Participant 1e *“Writing skill is like applying for a job. Because we pay great attention to grammar.”* stated that the German grammar rules are very important during the writing process. Participant 1k *“It is like developing knowledge. Because it requires using the grammatical structure in accordance with the rules while making sentences, which has an important place in the advancement of German.”* emphasized the development of grammar in writing skill. Participant 1k *“Writing is like math because we choose the right words according to the rules of writing, grammar, and then we have a simple equation.”* stated that the right choice of words in the writing process, the use of words in the right place, attention to the formal features of the language an equation was established in writing.

Table 15: Metaphors and Reasons for Giving Pleasure as you succeed Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Rain	Feeling good	
Make-up	Beautification while writing	
Bed	Be motivated by writing	Giving Pleasure
Playing ball	The more you write, the more you love	as you succeed
Eat	Be motivated by writing	
Friday	Not want to finish writing	
Book	Ability to use the language when writing	

In Table 15, metaphors of “rain, makeup, bed, playing ball, eat, friday, book” were developed in the category of pleasure as you succeed. Accordingly, it is seen that the students' desire to write increases when they are successful in the writing process. Participant 1k “*Writing skill is like rain. Because even if it looks like a bad thing, but it reminds me of good smell and makes me feel good.*” stated that she was actually biased about his writing skills but felt good when she succeeded. Participant 3k “*Writing skill is like playing ball. Because the more you go into it, the more time you spend with it, the more you love it.*” stressed that the more time she devotes to writing, the more she will be loved. Participant 3k “*writing skill is like eating. Because when you get pleasure, you write very much.*” stated that motivation increases when they are successful in the writing process.

Table 16: Metaphors and Reasons for Creativity Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Paint	Adding something from yourself	
Being creative	Recognizing creativity as you type	
Being a painter	Requires imagination	
Freedom	Be able to write about everything	Creativity
Sea	Transferring thoughts without stopping	
Poem	Be artistic	
Imagination	The necessity of imagination to write	
Dream	To push the limit of your imagination	

In Table 16, metaphors of “paint, being creative, being a painter, freedom, sea, poetry, imagination and dream” were developed in the category of creativity. When the reasons of metaphors are examined, it is seen that imagination is important in writing skills according to students' thoughts. Participant 1e “*Writing skill is like paint. Because it creates simple reality through the ways of narration, in a sense person occur to the reality by adding imagination to the world paints human.*” stated that the individual creates text according to his / her own imagination. Participant 4k “*Writing skill is like a dream. Because I push the limit of my imagination.*” emphasized that imagination is used in writing.

Table 17: Metaphors and Reasons for Freedom Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Clean Air	Being free while writing	Freedom
Communication	Using writing for communication	
The mirror of feelings	Transferring feelings more easily by writing	
Art	Being in a different world while writing	
Freedom	Writing on every subject	
Thinking	Transferring thoughts	

In Table 17, the metaphors of “clean air, freedom, communication, mirror of feelings, art, thining are included in the freedom category. With these metaphors, students tried to express that they could express their feelings and thoughts as they wanted during the writing process and that they were free to write on all subjects. Participant 1k *“writing is like freedom. Because you can express yourself more easily by writing.”* stated that thoughts are more easily expressed since there is no time limitation in writing skill. Participant 2k *“The ability to write is like a mirror of feelings. Because people can better convey themselves and their feelings by writing.”* emphasized that it is more comfortable to express yourself by writing. Participant 4k *“writing is like thought because it serves to convey thoughts.”* stated that writing have created a space for the person.

Table 18: Metaphors and Reasons for Creating Integrity Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Painting	Integrity while writing	Creating integrity
Latch	When you begin the subject, the rest comes	
Chain	Merging of each word with the next	
Build	Writing according to a specific plan	
Jigsaw	Formation of text as you write	
Poem	Writing meaningful and fluent	

In Table 18, the metaphors of “painting, latch, chain, build, jigsaw, poem were developed in the category of creating integrity. With these metaphors, the students stated that they could not write any text randomly, that the text should be planned in a plan and order and that an integrity should be formed without breaking the subject while writing. Participant 1e *“writing is like painting. Because it is necessary to create integrity in a composition.”* emphasized that there must be an integrity in the text. Participant 1k *“writing is like a latch. Because when you hold the subject, you realize that the rest is already here.”* stated that after logging in to writing comes the rest. Partizipant 4k *“writingis like a poetry. Because being able to write meaningfully and fluently produces great text.”* emphasized the importance of creating integrity in writing skills.

Table 19: Metaphors and Reasons for Requiring a lot of Labor, Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
First steps of a baby	Reaching the result hardly	Requiring a lot of Labor
Loop	Producing words and sentences while writing	
Art	Writing down what you know	
Attract Eyeliner	Distortion of text	
Field	The more labor you give, the more efficiency	
Mill	Formation of text as you type	
Learn language	Requires continuity	

In Table 19, metaphors of “first steps of baby, loop, art, attract eyeliner, field, mill, learn language” have been developed in the category of requiring a lot of labor. It is understood from these metaphors that according to the students, a lot of effort should be given to advance in writing skills and it is possible to use correct sentence structures as they write. Participant 1k *“writing is like the first steps of a baby. Because a lot of work has been done, the result has been reached by falling off.”* stated that the acquisition of writing skills is very slow and requires a lot of labor. Participant 4k *“Writing skills are like fields. Because the more language you put into labor, the more efficient you can write.”* emphasized that writing skills were successful as long as the knowledge of language was sufficient. Participant 2e *“writing skills are like attracting eyeliner. Because the eyeliner that is not drawn properly bothers the same way in the text that is not written properly.”* stated that the product is bad when it is not written according to a certain integrity and rules.

Table 20: Metaphors and Reasons for Being the most Important Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
The basis of language	Binding in development of other skills	Being the most Important
Vital organ	To be the most important skill	
Eat	Some things are missing without him	
Heartless body	To understand the language by writing	
Basic stone	The basis of skills	
Branches of a flower	Lack of language without writing	

In Table 20, being the most important category includes the metaphors of “the basis of language, vital organ, eat, heartless body, basic stone, branches of a flower”. According to these metaphors, it is understood that writing skill is the most important skill in language learning compared to four basic language skills and forms the basis of language. Participant 1k *“writing is the basis of language. Because if you can’t write, you can’t talk. It is the most important skill. Listening, reading and speaking skills depend on writing skills.”* stated that writing skill is the most important among the four basic language skills and that the development of other skills depends on writing skill. Participant 2k *“writing is like a vital organ. Because we produce products throughout our lives, writing skills are one of the most important skills for this.”* emphasized that it is important that a product emerges in the writing process. Participant 3e *“writing is like a heartless body. Because if we don’t have*

writing skills, we can't understand that language." stated that writing skills are necessary to understand the language.

Table 21: Metaphors and Reasons for Being the Easiest Way to Express Thoughts

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Communication	Communicating in writing despite barriers	Being the Easiest Way to Express Thoughts
Life	Being the easiest way to express thoughts and emotions	
Freedom	No obstacles as long as you can write	
Art	Expressing your inner world	
Mirror	Reflecting thoughts	

In Table 21, "communication, life, freedom, art, mirror" metaphors have been developed in the category of being the easiest way to express thoughts. As it is understood from these metaphors and reasons, it is seen that communication is more easily established since it is easier to control the factors such as instant response in writing skill and choice of correct words. Participant 1k *"writing skill is like life. Because writing is the easiest way to express feelings and thoughts "* stated that thoughts are easier to express with writing. Participant 1k *"writing skills are like communication because even if we have some obstacles, we can apply to writing to communicate."* they stated that despite the barriers, it makes the communication process possible.

Table 22: Metaphors and Reasons for Being Permanent Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
A stain that leaves a mark	To be permanent	Being
Tattoo	To be permanent	Permanent
Letter	Effective even if it is outdated	

In Table 22, in the category of being permanent included "a stain that leaves a mark, tattoo, letter " metaphors. Participant 1k *"writing is like a tattoo. Because writing is permanent. It is important to write down what we know and hear."* emphasized that writing is permanent. Participant 2k *"writing is like a letter. Because it is still effective even if it is outdated."* have stated the effectiveness of writing.

Table 23: Metaphors and Reasons for Learning New Things Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Stairs	Developing as you write	Learning New Things
Putting information on paper	Reflecting all you know about German	
Soil	To be productive	
Tree	Development of writing	
Production	Processing words and grammar in the mind	
Sport	Progress	
Snowball	Developing as you write	
Intelligence	To be functional	

In Table 23, metaphors of “stairs, putting information on paper, soil, tree, production, sports, snowball, intelligence” have been developed in the category of learning new things. It is understood from these metaphors that writing skill is a production process for students. Participant 3k *“writing is like production. Because words and grammar are processed in the mind.”* emphasized that grammar and words are processed in the mind in writing skills and created product. Participant 4e *“writing is like snowballs. because as you write, you progress”* stated that increased knowledge of language in the writing process. Participant 3k *“writing is like intelligence. Because it is functional.”* emphasized writing skills are functional.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, it has been tried to obtain cognitive and psychological essences for reading and writing skills by examining how pre-service German teachers perceive German reading and writing skills, both their own experiences and their experiences in related courses. It was seen that pre-service teachers developed 58 metaphors related to reading skill. These metaphors were grouped under 10 categories: “development, vocabulary learning, opening up to different worlds, giving pleasure, being difficult to understand, removing from context, working the brain, requiring continuity, developing pronunciation, being important”. In general, the categories of “development, vocabulary learning, opening up to different worlds, giving pleasure, removing from context, working the brain, requiring continuity, developing pronunciation, being important” were evaluated as positive; the category of “being difficult to understand” can be considered negative. It can be said that the students' positive perceptions of reading skills are more than the negative ones. In the development category, participants emphasized that reading increases the speed of reading and understanding. In the vocabulary learning category, participants emphasized that new vocabulary was learned during the reading process. In the categories of opening up to different worlds, they emphasized that they recognize different perspectives with each text and that they become acquainted with different worlds and cultures while reading. In giving pleasure category, participants expressed their willingness to read when they understood the text. Therefore, it can be said that students' reading comprehension motivates them to read and their motivation increases. In the category of removing from the context is emphasized that when they did not know all the foreign words, they imposed meanings on the unknown words from the flow of the event in the text. This is evidence that students develop strategies in reading skills. Because the students tried to understand and interpret the unknown from the known situation here. Again in this category, the participants emphasized that the meanings imposed on the text are not the only ones, they vary from person to person. In this case, it can be said that the students interpreted the content of the text in reading skill by taking into consideration the reception aesthetics. Because in the reception aesthetics, the reader comprehends and interprets the

text according to himself/herself (Özbek, 2005). Therefore, students can interpret the text according to their own perception frames and backgrounds.

In the category of brain training, participants emphasized that the brain is constantly dynamic as a result of the brain being confronted with too many stimuli during the reading process. They also emphasized that the meanings of the symbols were extracted from the person's brain and that the previously learned grammar rules were seen as concrete in the text and that these rules were reinforced. Participants pointed out that there should be a stable continuity in reading skills in the category of requiring continuity. It was emphasized that progress could be achieved if the reading action was sustained, and that reading and comprehension skills might decline when reading was interrupted. In addition, it is stated that the desire to read will increase if the reading action is carried out continuously.

In the category of developing pronunciation, participants emphasized that reading skill contributes to the way in which words come out, to make emphasis and intonation, and to pronounce correctly. In the category of being important, participants pointed out that reading skills are important and that language as a system cannot work without reading and be useful. Although reading is suggested as a receptive skill (Lutjeharms & Schmidt, 2010; Johnson, A., 2018) in the literature, that students do not enter into a production process such as speaking and writing skills, it is understood from the data obtained in this study that they have developed an active mental process in order to understand the text both structurally and contextually in the reading process. As mentioned above, only one negative category about reading skills was developed in this study. This category is being difficult to understand. In this category, the participants emphasized that there are complex word and sentence structures in reading texts and that the meaning becomes difficult if the text is deep.

It was seen that the pre-service teachers developed 61 metaphors related to the writing skill. These metaphors are classified under 11 categories: "difficulty, giving importance to grammar, giving pleasure as you succeed, creativity, freedom, creating integrity, requiring a lot of labor, being the most important, being the easiest way to express thoughts, being permanent, learning new things". The categories of "giving importance to grammar, giving pleasure as you succeed, creativity, freedom, creating integrity, being the most important, being the easiest way to express thoughts, being permanent, learning new things" were evaluated as positive; the category of "difficulty, requiring a lot of labor" can be considered negative. In the category of being difficult, participants pointed out that it is difficult to write in accordance with grammar rules, that writing skills cannot be acquired in a short time and that there is no limit to writing. In another negative category, which requires a lot of labor, the participants emphasized that the acquisition of writing skills can be achieved as a result of a lot of effort and they stated that continuity is very important in the acquisition of this skill. In the "giving importance to grammar" category, participants emphasized that they attach great importance to grammar when writing, that they also learn grammar during the writing process and that they use the grammatical structures they previously learned. The participants expressed

in the category of “giving pleasure as you succeed” that they felt very good when they wrote a text in a foreign language as they succeeded and their motivation towards writing increased. In the creativity category, the participants emphasized the importance of creating text according to the knowledge and imagination in the writing process, and the ability to write in any subject without limiting the person. The participants stated that feelings and thoughts were more easily expressed in the freedom category and therefore communication could be better in this way. In creating integrity category, the participants emphasized that thoughts cannot be written randomly in the writing process, there should be harmony between the sentences, the rest of the text is easier to complete after entering the writing, and a writing plan should be made in the first place. In the category of being the most important, the participants stated that writing skill is binding on the development of other language skills, and that without writing, language cannot be comprehended and it is the most important skill.

In the category of being the easiest way to express thoughts, participants stated that writing is the easiest way to convey thoughts to the other party if there are obstacles in verbal communication environments. The participants mentioned the persistence of something written in the category of being permanent due to the fact that the probability of forgetting is less than what is said. In the learning new things category, participants emphasized that writing improves German knowledge, grammar and words are processed in the mind during the writing process and it is a productive skill. The common views on reading and writing skills are that both skills require continuity, are important, be enjoyable and difficult.

In the study of Tiryaki and Demir's metaphoric perceptions of Turkish teacher candidates about writing skills, the freedom category was developed as obtained in this study (2016). In the study of metaphorical perceptions of Turkish teacher candidates related to critical writing by Topçuoğlu Ünal and Tekin, “multidimensional thinking, objectivity, equal treatment” categories were obtained (2013). In the study in which the views of students and teachers about language skills in teaching Turkish as a foreign language were evaluated, according to the opinions of teachers and students it was concluded that one of the most needed language skills to be developed was reading (Yıldız, 2015). In a study where the perceptions of graduate students on academic writing skills were investigated, were developed the metaphors “a challenging process, an action requiring expertise, a multi-rule action, an action requiring language and expression, an action that is disliked, an action that gives pleasure, a process of producing new things geliştiril were developed (Aydın & Baysan, 2018).

In this study, the categories developed for writing skills are “difficult, giving importance to grammar, giving pleasure as they succeed, and requiring a lot of labor” are similar to the categories of Aydın and Baysan. In addition, Güney found that the most challenging writing methods and techniques were creative writing, rewriting the text, critical writing, and writing from a pool of words (2016). In the study that Turkish teacher candidates' comprehension levels and misconceptions about writing concepts were

investigated, it was concluded that Turkish teacher candidates' comprehension levels and misconceptions about writing concepts were insufficient (Çevik Ceran, 2015)

5. Recommendations

According to the results of this research, the following suggestions can be made;

- Firstly, what the skills are in the context of a foreign language should theoretically be explained to prospective teachers. Awareness should be created for the students.
- This skill should be turned into a productive skill with the texts in which students can play an active role in reading skill.
- Attention should be paid to ensure that the depths and difficulty levels of the selected texts are appropriate to the students' level in order to improve their reading skills. Therefore, the likelihood of developing a negative perception regarding this skill is also reduced.
- Writing methods and techniques should be applied to the students practically.

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DETERMINATION OF METAPHORIC PERCEPTIONS OF GERMAN TEACHER CANDIDATES
IN THE TURKEY TOWARDS GERMAN READING AND WRITING SKILLS

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